

CORRIGENDUM TO
EXTENDING A RECENT RESULT OF SANTOS ON PARTITIONS
INTO ODD PARTS

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Corrigendum

In *Extending a Recent Result of Santos on Partitions into Odd Parts*, INTEGERS 3 (2003), paper A4, the author states and proves the following theorem (which is a generalization of a theorem proven by Santos):

Theorem 1.2. *Let $K = (k_2, k_3, k_4, \dots)$ be an infinite vector of nonnegative integers. Define $p(n; K)$ as the number of partitions of n of the form $p_1 + p_2 + p_3 + p_4 + \dots$ with $p_1 \geq p_2 \geq p_3 \geq p_4 \cdots \geq 0$ and $p_1 \geq k_2 p_2 + k_3 p_3 + k_4 p_4 + \dots$. Then, for all $n \geq 0$, $p(n; K)$ equals the number of partitions of n whose parts must be 1's or of the form $(\sum_{i=2}^m k_i) + (m - 1)$ for some integer $m \geq 2$.*

It has recently been brought to the author's attention that this theorem is slightly incorrect. Namely, the parameter k_2 must be positive; that is, we must assume $k_2 \geq 1$. Note that all other parameters $k_i, i \geq 3$, are allowed to be nonnegative. Note also that the proof technique utilized in the paper is still valid (as long as $k_2 \geq 1$). Thus, no other portions of the paper are affected by this change.